

Subject:

Development Studies

Title:

**Development and Displacement: A Case Study of
Mallannasagar Reservoir Oustees**

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Abstract:

Development is the first initiation, whereas Displacement is considered as the outcome of the development. The displacement is caused due to the expansion of the plans of the state in terms of development of infrastructure, provision of welfare facilities and the construction of dams which have created huge adverse effects. The irrigational development projects not only cause fragmented riverine ecosystems and forest ecosystems but also adversely effects on livelihood of the people. Thus, the development, either spontaneous or induced, brings not only benefits but also often causes social disruption in terms of severe environmental, social and economic problems.

In the above context, the scholars have undertaken this study on the impact of irrigation development projects in post Telangana in terms of geographical, economic and social costs which people have suffered. The paper examines how the relocation of the people from their dwellings, property of fertile lands, customs and traditions, religious heritage centres in the name of so-called development, has been done. The primary data was collected from displaced people from Mallannasagar reservoir under the Kaleshwaram Project. The secondary data of various reports of State and Central Governments and other independent sources is taken into consideration for the study.

Keywords:

Development, Displacement, Irrigation Projects, fragmented riverine system, forest ecosystems, livelihood of the people.

Introduction:

The formation of new state of Telangana on 2nd June, 2014 is a long-cherished desire of people of Telangana and is an achievement owing to the historical struggles and sacrifices of the people of Telangana. After the achievement of Statehood, the Telangana State Government has significantly concentrated on agricultural development through the construction of new irrigation projects and the developing of existing projects.

As part of the development in Telangana where more than 65 percent of the people are depending on agriculture, providing the water facility has become one of the major issues that the State Government has to address. Therefore, the State of Telangana has initiated new projects for the development of irrigation facilities. The development of Irrigation in Telangana is mostly dependent on two major rivers, Godavari and Krishna.

The Telangana Government has focused on completing 33 Major and Medium Irrigation ongoing and proposed projects on River Godavari on top most priority and also restoration of Minor irrigation tanks. With such huge and many projects being undertaken, there bound to be large scale displacement and its consequences.

Objectives:

1. To study the significance of Development of Irrigational Projects in Telangana State.
2. To examine the extent of Development Induced Displacement.
3. To examine the impact of Displacement on the livelihood of effected people in terms of geographical, economic and social consequences.

Methodology:

The primary data has been collected from 100 respondents of Kishtapur, Vemulaghat and Laxmapur villages of Mallannasagar reservoir through structured questionnaire. The relevant secondary data is collected from the reports of State and Central Governments, Socio-Economic Outlook of Telangana Government, Journals and other independent sources.

Significance of Development of Irrigational Projects in Telangana State

The term “Development” envisages a battery of changes, changes for the betterment of the community. It involves the notion of growth and uplift of the welfare of the collective. Development activity and is a continuous process for the progress of society. The primary purpose of any Irrigation Project is to reduce poverty, improve food security, create local employment, increase household income and enhance the sustainability of the land use.

Ever since the state is formed, the Telangana Government has promised to fulfil three objectives. These include Water resources through irrigation development, financial resources and increasing employment in the state. Among all these objectives, the state government has given much emphasis on development of irrigation projects. The agriculture sector, which has grown on average by 14.5% annually for the last five years, has helped to mitigate the economic impact of COVID-19 and it reflects the Government’s relentless efforts to increase farmer income.

Development of Projects in Telangana State

With the aim to irrigate one crore acres in the state of Telangana, the Telangana government has put efforts to complete all the major and minor projects and bridge the gap in irrigation potential by renovating existing irrigation infrastructure and restoring age-old irrigation tanks that are the lifeline for the rural economy. The Telangana government has to focus on completing the 33 (No of) Major & Medium Irrigation ongoing and proposed projects on River Godavari on top most priority and also restoration of Minor Irrigation tanks.

The irrigation projects in Telangana state are classified into 3 categories. The Ayacut covering less than or equal to 5000 acres is classified as a Minor project. While a project holding 5000 acres to 25000 is classified as a Medium project. The project holding more than 25000 acres is classified as Major Project.

Development Induced Displacement:

Displacement of human settlement is not a new phenomenon. It has been caused by a variety of factors like Construction of dams, hydroelectric complexes, establishment of industries, exploration of minerals and mining etc. It is very important to understand that the displacement is a multi-dimensional phenomenon of which physical relocation is only one of the most significant outcomes.

In this context, displacement refers not only to those who are forced to physically relocate in order to make way for the project but also includes those who are displaced from their livelihoods. It is commonly experienced through the loss of land and the disruption of social and economic relationships. Development-induced displacement as a result of the construction of infrastructure projects, including large dams, is characterized by the permanent relocation of all households within a geographic area. Thus, if development is one side of the coin, displacement is the other.

Development induced Displacement in Telangana

Table-1

Displacement statistics of select projects in Telangana

Conflict ridden reservoirs	Households directly affected (total project)	Affected Area (in acres)	Starting year of land conflict	Legal processes and loopholes enabling the conflict
Baswapur Reservoir	2000	3780	2016	Violation of LARR Act
Kondapochamma Reservoir	1059	4636	2016	Non-rehabilitation of displaced people, Violation of LARR Act, Delay in compensation, Non-payment of promised compensation
Gouravelli reservoir	684	4167	2015	Non-rehabilitation of displaced people, Delay in compensation, Incorrect estimation of compensation, Violation of LARR Act.
Komaravelly Mallanasagar reservoir	2819	13,962	2016	Non-rehabilitation of displaced people, Controversial land acquisition by the government, Violation of free prior informed consent, Violation of LARR Act, Incorrect estimation of compensation
Annapurna reservoir	989	2,469	2020	Non-rehabilitation of displaced people, Controversial land acquisition by the government

Source: Telangana state department of Irrigation and CAD, 2021

The data presented in table-1 highlights on project wise people who were directly affected by displacement, land affected by irrigation and legal processes and conflicts raised. Results clearly reveal that, apart from land is being lost, thousands of villagers depending on the land for livelihood and employment were forcefully displaced and, in many cases, the legal processes had not been supportive to the victims who have lost their lands due to forceful displacement.

Impact of Displacement on the livelihood of effected people in terms of geographical, economic and social (consequences)

For the present study, scholar has selected the field area of Mallannasagar Reservoir (Siddipet District) under Kaleswaram lift irrigation project. This reservoir has been built to provide water for agriculture, industrial and drinking purpose. The villages which have been submerged under this reservoir are Etigadda, Kistapur, and Vemulaghat, along with six villages- Lakshmapur, Brahmana Bandarupalli, Erravalli, Singaram, Palla Pahad and Rampur. In this regard, an attempt is made to examine the respondent's profile in terms of age, caste, education, occupation and income status. This profile will help to understand the level of severity among the cross section of people as respondents, facing due to project effected displacement.

Age Wise distribution of Respondents

Sl.No	Age	No.of respondents	Percentage
1	21-30	16	16
2	31-40	26	26
3	41-50	19	19
4	51-60	21	21
5	61 and above	18	18
	Total	100	100

The above table shows the age particulars of the respondents. Total 100 respondents nearly 61 percentage are in the age group of 21 to 50. This is the productive age but they are affected due to displacement and have lost their livelihood. The remaining 39 percent at the age group between 51 and above became dependent and they have been in pitiable condition. The respondents who lost their livelihood, have to bear the responsibilities of their elder dependents.

Age with caste wise distribution of respondents

Age/caste	SC	ST	BC	OC	Total
21-30	03	05	06	02	16
31-40	06	08	09	03	26
41-50	05	06	07	01	19
51-60	08	07	06	-	21
61 and Above	05	04	07	02	18
Total	27	30	35	08	100

This table indicates that majority i.e., 35 percentage of respondents belong to Backward class, 30 percent are from STs, 27 percent are from SCs and the very less percentage i.e., 08 are from OCs. In the age group of 21-50, which is of productive age, 22 respondents are BCs. Next to this 19 percent are STs, 14 percent are SCs and very less percentage is OCs i.e., 06. The highest number of people is BCs (who have not only) lost their livelihood and (but) also caste occupation. Remaining respondents have also lost their livelihood and caste related professional employment.

Educational status of respondents

Sl.no	Education	No.of respondents	Percentage
1	Illiterate	11	11
2	Primary education	21	21
3	Secondary education	17	17
4	Intermediate	15	15
5	Graduation	14	14

6	Post-graduation	12	12
7	Others	10	10
	Total	100	100

This table reflects the educational status of the respondents. Out of 100 respondents; nearly 50 percent (completed) secondary school education. They completely depend either on their agricultural lands (or) working as agricultural (labourers). (Of the) Remaining 50 percent, 10 percent are diploma holders and having other basic level courses, and (the remaining) 40 percent are above SSC level (who depend) on agriculture.

Occupational status of respondents

Sl.no	Occupation	No.of respondents	Percentage
1	Agriculture	42	42
2	Labour	27	27
3	Private job	17	17
4	Government job	04	04
5	No source of income	10	10
	Total	100	100

(above table depicts) the distribution of sample (respondents) based on (their) occupations. Out of 100 respondents, 69 percentage of respondents depend on agriculture (as farmers and labourers as well). 17 percent respondents are doing private job and only 04 percent are in government jobs. The remaining 10 percent respondents are dependents (without any own source of income). This indicates the fact that displacement will certainly have a huge influence on the (lively-hood) of the respondents.

Income level of respondents

Sl.no	Income per annum	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Less than Rs.2 Lakh	40	40
2	Rs.2 lakh – Rs.4 Lakh	35	35
3	Rs.4 lakh – Rs.6 lakhs	12	12
4	Rs.6 lakh and above	05	05
5	Dependents	08	08
	Total	100	100

(the above) table shows the sample respondents of different categories based on income capacity per annum. Majority of the respondents i.e., 40 percent have income of less than Rs. 2 lakhs. 35 percent of respondents are having income level between Rs.2 lakh to Rs.4 lakh, very less percentage i.e., 05 are having Rs.6 lakh and above. (This further indicates that the displaced respondents have minimal income range and displacement has certainly had very bad influence on their livelihood).

Impact of Irrigation Projects in terms of Geographical, Economic and Social (Consequences):

The report of Cernea (1999) submitted to World Bank has prescribed the eight possible interrelated possible risks that may emerge from displacement. These are:

- I. **Food Insecurity:** Loss of shelter and jobs will result in inability of financial strength to procure food for their families. This will result in chronic undernourishment and further may result in low calorie protein intake levels of children in families
- II. **Homelessness:** Due to the initiation of project development, the people who have lost their lands because of construction of projects may suffer from loss of shelter. In many cases, homelessness creates huge stress to the family members and loss of homes will also result in deprivation of social togetherness.
- III. **Increased Mortality:** The social stress and psychological trauma, caused due to forced development-Induced displacement may result in increased morbidity and mortality.
- IV. **Joblessness:** The people especially dependent on the conventional forms of employment in their home towns/villages will lose their jobs due to the project development. In India majority of the projects constructed in rural areas resulted in loss of jobs to those who depend on agriculture over the years.
- V. **Landlessness:** Due to the expropriation of land for the development of the project, the main foundation for livelihood and the productive system is lost and this has made a huge impact on the progress of the people.
- VI. **Loss of access to common property:** People sharing the common property such as access to water bodies, burial grounds, quarries (would suffer) due to development induced displacement.
- VII. **Marginalization:** When families lose their economic power due to projects, it may result in downward mobility. Sometimes marginalization's impact may be on social and psychological aspects of the people.
- VIII. **Social Disintegration:** Displacement will have an effect on social disintegration especially when people are forcibly shifted, trade linkages, life sustaining networks will get dismantled.

Conclusion:

Ever since the formation of Telangana, the State Government has emphasized more on development of projects as one of the keys (instruments) for developing the state. Towards this end, several irrigation projects have been initiated with an objective to provide water for irrigation, drinking and for other purposes. The study on development (induced displacement) impact reveals that (though) the development projects in Telangana have benefited the people hugely in terms of providing water to crops. Yet the development induced displacement has brought many miseries to the people.

Further, (huge fertile) land has been utilized for the construction of projects and the results prove that many of the displaced people are yet to receive the compensation, rehabilitation and resettlement benefits.

Overall, the study concludes that in order to achieve the goals to develop water resources, the irrigation projects remained one of the top priorities and at the same time, the government has the responsibility to reduce the ill effects caused in the form of displacement and (its consequences) due to development of projects in Telangana.

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